

Use of chloramine-T for the determination of thiophosphate pesticides

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A quick and convenient method involving the use of chloramine-T has been developed for determination of thiophosphate group of pesticides e.g. parathion, methyl parathion, fenthion and fenitrothion in technical products and in their formulations.

The pesticides are a group of chemicals intended for preventing/destroying any pest detrimental to man or his interest during production, processing, storage, transportation and distribution of food. Thiophosphate pesticides are the most effective insecticides and are used to control a wide variety of insect pests. Because of better insecticidal activity, their determination has widely been studied¹⁻⁷. In the present method, we describe a simple titrimetric method for the determination of some thiophosphate group of pesticides at milligram level. Parathion, methyl parathion, fenthion and fenitrothion have been determined in technical form and in their formulations using chloramine-T reagent in acidic medium. The proposed method can be eas-

ily adopted in an ordinary laboratory for the assay of such compounds.

Results and discussion

The prescribed concentration of the reagent (0.1 N) and the reaction time (10 min) was found to be suitable for accurate results. For lower concentration and lower time period the recovery of the sample has lower value, because of incomplete reaction. However, a more concentrated reagent solution (0.2–1.0 N) and higher reaction time (12–60 min) has no effect on recovery. The reaction proceeds smoothly at room temperature (25–27°C) and at higher temperature (40–80°C) gave inaccurate results, because of the decom-

Table 1. Determination of some thiophosphate group of pesticides in technical products and formulation with chloramine-T reagent

Sl. no.	Sample	Aliquots taken (ml)	Amount present (mg)	Amount obtained by calen* (mg)	Standard deviation (SD)	Coefficient of variation (CV) (%)
1.	Parathion Tech. (92%)	1.0	0.92	0.911	0.0007	0.0768
		3.0	2.76	2.741	0.0012	0.0438
		5.0	4.60	4.576	0.0007	0.0153
(a)	Parathion W.P. (25%)	1.0	0.25	0.248	0.0007	0.2839
		3.0	0.75	0.745	0.0007	0.0939
		5.0	1.25	1.245	0.0012	0.0964
(b)	Parathion E.C. (50%)	1.0	0.50	0.496	0.0007	0.1411
		3.0	1.50	1.489	0.0010	0.0672
		5.0	2.50	2.489	0.0010	0.0402
2.	Methyl parathion Tech. (80%)	1.0	0.80	0.793	0.0007	0.0883
		3.0	2.40	0.745	0.0007	0.0939
		5.0	4.00	3.983	0.0012	0.0301
(a)	Methyl parathion W.P. (25%)	1.0	0.20	0.248	0.0007	0.2822
		3.0	0.75	0.745	0.0007	0.0939
		5.0	0.25	1.244	0.0012	0.0965
(b)	Methyl parathion E.C. (50%)	1.0	0.50	0.495	0.0010	0.2020
		3.0	1.50	1.489	0.0012	0.0806
		5.0	2.50	2.491	0.0007	0.0281

3.	Fenthion Tech. (96%)	1.0	0.96	0.952	0.0007	0.0735
		3.0	2.88	2.863	0.0007	0.0244
		5.0	4.80	4.783	0.0023	0.0481
(a)	Fenthion W.P. (25%)	1.0	0.25	0.248	0.0007	0.2822
		3.0	0.75	0.745	0.0007	0.0939
		5.0	1.25	1.245	0.0007	0.0562
(b)	Fenthion E.C. (50%)	1.0	0.50	0.496	0.0007	0.1411
		3.0	1.50	1.489	0.0007	0.0470
		5.0	2.50	2.489	0.0010	0.0402
4.	Fenitrothion Tech. (80%)	1.0	0.80	0.793	0.0007	0.0883
		3.0	2.40	2.381	0.0012	0.0504
		5.0	4.00	3.983	0.0012	0.0301

*Each value is average of nine determinations.

For all the compounds the reaction time is 10 min and stoichiometry is 2.

position of the reagent.

The results given in Table 1 reveal that the proposed method could be suitable for the determination of some thiophosphate pesticides in technical products and formulations. The values of standard deviation (SD) and coefficient of variation (CV) indicate that the suggested method is reproducible and precise.

The stoichiometry of the reagent with all the samples is the same because of their structural similarity. Taking parathion (*O,O*-diethyl-*O*-4-nitrophenylthiophosphate) as a model compound, a probable course of reaction has been suggested.

Similar reaction has been proposed for all the thiophosphate pesticides (methyl parathion (*O,O*-dimethyl-*O*-4-nitrophenyl thiophosphate), fenthion (*O,O*-dimethyl-*O*-4-methylmercapto-3-methylphenylthiophosphate) and fenitrothion (*O,O*-dimethyl-*O*-4-nitro-3-methylphenylthiophosphate)).

Experimental

The reagents and chemicals used were of analytical grade, chloramine-T (M & B, 0.1 *N*), sodium thiosulphate (B.D.H., 0.1 *N*), copper sulphate (G.R., 0.1 *N*), glacial acetic acid (Merck), potassium iodide (A.R., 10%) and starch (1%) solutions were used.

Stock solutions of technical thiophosphate pesticides were made by dissolving accurately weighed amount of the sample in appropriate solvent. Parathion (tech) was selected as a test sample. 100 mg of the sample was weighed accurately and dissolved in minimum amount of glacial acetic acid (5 ml) in a stoppered conical flask. The solution was then transferred into 100 ml volumetric flask and glacial acetic acid was added up to the mark (100 ml). Similarly, the stock solutions of technical methyl parathion, fenthion and fenitrothion were also prepared. In case of formulations, the stock solutions were made, as described above for technical products.

Procedure: An aliquot containing 1–5 mg of the sample was taken in a 100 ml Erlenmeyer flask followed by the addition of 5 ml of 0.1 *N* chloramine-T solution and 5 ml of glacial acetic acid. The flask was stoppered and the contents were allowed to react at room temperature (25–27°C) for prescribed reaction time (10 min). To this reaction mixture 5 ml of potassium iodide (10%) solution was added and titrated against standardised 0.1 *N* sodium thiosulphate solution to starch end point. A blank experiment was also run under identical conditions using all the reagents except the sample. The amount of the sample was calculated by the usual method.

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